

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: FAGAN****FIRST NAME: GREGORY****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA**

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Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)*The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:*The author did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)The author did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

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List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP):

1. The process of writing (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 2021, 7)
2. Early Start-Up Organizing ideas (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 7)
3. Researching and Organizing Ideas (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 7-8)
4. The preliminary Plan (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 9)
5. Writing the Essay (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 10-11)
6. In-Text citing (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 35-36)
7. Presenting Data in Tables (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 53-54)

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RESPONSE PAPER FOR INTERNATIONAL ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

Scholarly research must be presented in a neutral, professional style that adheres to specific stylistic standards to communicate academic work effectively (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 7). As I continue my PhD studies, I'll need to learn more about academic writing if I want to be able to articulate ideas supported by facts in a clear and persuasive way. This course, International Academic Writing (ACA-401D), which introduces students to scholarly writing, has provided me with a variety of tools, standards, and recommendations that I will work to incorporate into my future academic endeavors. I'll discuss five of these important ideas in this first response paper (RP) that I feel are important to being able to write professionally and persuasively.

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2) RESEARCHING AND ORGANIZING IDEAS

The first chapter of the course materials goes on to discuss a highly critical and simple to remember flow for essay writing. Remembering that **the process is not "rigidly linear" is crucial** while considering these topics (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 7). There could be moments when the author has to reassess while writing the essay. However, the following three fundamental stages must be followed to guarantee that a topic does not add prejudice or diverge into several directions that make the writing difficult to follow: Early Start-Up, Question Definition, and Initial Plan Drafting.

Making sure there is adequate **time to study, ponder, and write about a topic throughout the early stages of a project is essential** (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 7). An academic essay cannot be written in one sitting, and procrastination might result in a hastily written document without any sense of logic.

Research and the organizing of ideas begin with a question, and as stated in the course material, "... evaluating and presenting the answers to the questions is vital" (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 7). The research topic should constantly be in the forefront of the author's mind as the **investigation progresses and evidence is produced** (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 9). The generated evidence must be well-researched and should support the research topic.

Drafting a preliminary strategy might start after we have the information we need to support our thesis. **A preliminary plan or outline may be created if the aforementioned steps have been followed** to guarantee that we have a logical flow to address our research issue (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 9). Here, we may start outlining the narrative we're attempting to convey, figuring out whether we need any extra proof, and determining how our work will advance the field we're researching.

3) WRITING THE ESSAY

Once we have created our outline and have the content, which may come in a variety of formats like references or in-text tables, we start to create our first draft. The coursepack's reading assignment states that **"the draft is like the raw material you improve via editing and redrafting"** (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 10). This assertion is absolutely accurate, and it offers a helpful perspective on the writing process. The starting point for structuring the article logically in this situation is our evidence, which serves as the raw material. Each piece of supporting evidence should strengthen our claims.

The fundamental organization of our essay should include an introduction, a body, and a conclusion (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 10). The beginning should include a brief review of our issue and establish our argument, followed by a few simple yet powerful sentences on the major themes of our essay.

The essay's main body might be thought of as the **foundation upon which our argument is built** (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 10). We build a narrative that is backed up by our data and citations in an effort to address our research questions.

The conclusion will emphasize the "takeaway" or importance of the debate while also reiterating the key points of the article. Our thesis should be restated, along with the implications of our findings and potential future research directions.

4) IN-TEXT CITATIONS - QUOTATIONS AND PARAPHRASING

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Giving acknowledgment to our sources and avoiding plagiarism both depend on properly citing pertinent material in our essay. As described in the course pack, we need to be aware of the differences and usage of in-text citations. Every piece of information we use or cite from inside our work must be **credited by way of an in-text citation** (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 35). This citation will direct the reader to the original work so they can see where we received our knowledge. The readings for the course explain and show how to format direct quotes and paraphrased sentences.

a) Quotations

Quoting is the act of immediately incorporating the words of the original author into your own writing, generally after a signal phrase. Quotes must always be credited (and denoted by quotation marks), and you must add a page number to identify where the quote is located in the source. Quotes are used "when there is especially strong language in the quote that emphasizes the meaning very well" (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 36).

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b) Paraphrases

To paraphrase is to reword information from a source. To prevent giving the appearance that we are stealing someone else's ideas, in-text citations are equally vital here as they are with quotes. It should be noted that paraphrasing is not simply the rearrangement of sentences to appear different, but rather should be your own interpretation of the idea (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 36).

5) PRESENTING DATA IN TABLES

Statistical information can be presented via figures and tables to simplify complicated information and support an argument, as opposed to being discussed in the text (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 53). The American Psychological Association's handbook of style offers suggestions on how to present tables and figures correctly, focusing on headers, labeling, space, and numerical formatting.

Working to ensure that the table reflects the topic in the paragraph above it is one of the most crucial lessons to learn from this. I have seen in many past experiences, data presented in table format only to have been more of a distraction due to its complexities and poor labeling and having nothing to do with the discussion points. Presenting the correct data for the correct discussion point is an art as it is a science.

6) UNDERSTANDING STYLE GUIDES

Style guides provide essential instructions that, if followed, can help writers create work whose organization is clear to other readers. In particular, EUCLID advises following the Chicago (Turabian) standards and using American English. Coherence and consistency in a final work are made possible by using common forms and styles of writing (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 41).

I find that following style manuals improve my thought process, especially when writing on a certain subject. I will also be able to demonstrate my abilities to write clearly and effectively by using the templates offered by EUCLID. I've had issues with this in the past, so I'm looking forward to the writing assignments that will be supplied to help me become a better academic writer.

7) CONCLUSION

As I begin my Ph.D. studies in international public health, I am becoming more and more conscious of how important it is to be able to articulate ideas clearly via the art of academic writing in order to contribute to the field. I've discovered through the course materials for ACA-401D, period one, that mastering style and effective argumentation will be crucial. And even though this is just the first of many classes, I am grateful for the chance to review my writing abilities.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth edition. Bangui: Euclid University.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
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